
JORDAN'S PERSPECTIVE ON CLIMATE-DRIVEN RISKS

Author Rami Jacob Kakish
Date of Submission 01/09/2021
DOI 10.5281/zenodo.14566254

Table of Contents

1. Introduction (Water, climate, settlement patterns, and agricultural situation)	1
The Economy, Water and Climate	1
Settlement Patterns	2
2. Jordan Emission Profile	2
3. Jordan's Climate-Driven Risks Profile	2
Future Climate Projections	2
Four Climate Hazards	3
Sectoral Vulnerabilities	3
4. Tipping Point and Policy Recommendations	4
References	4

1. Introduction (Water, climate, settlement patterns, and agricultural situation)

The Economy, Water and Climate

Jordan is an upper-middle-income country (World Bank, 2021), at the crossroads between Asia, Africa, and Europe, lies in the Levant region. Jordan is a net food-importing developing country (WTO, 2020) and almost landlocked, with a limited coastline in the Gulf of Aqaba. The economy of Jordan depends on trade, international donations and loans, and foreign remittances. The latter accounts for approximately 20% of the GDP. (Government of the Netherlands,2019) (USAID 2017)

In Jordan, climate change has been an increasingly popular topic, not only within the non-governmental and, mostly western, donor countries' agencies in Amman, but a not so unusual tea-table talk among the public. A series of public-opinion and livelihood-altering events Jordanians have lived and have been living through the recent years have been drawing the public's attention to climate change. From flash floods in the major cities, and hiking canyons, such events had a hefty death toll and material losses (the latter debated among the public whether it was mere administrative negligence, unusual flash flood, or a mix of both), to volatile annual rainfall, and frequent droughts in a country heavily depending on upstream nations for water sources (Rajsekhar et al., 2017).All that is aggravating the water stress, affecting day-to-day chores of inhabitants, shrinking agricultural employment, potentially triggering rural to urban migration (UNDP, 2021) leading to expedited urban growth and rural depopulation (Britannica, 2021)(Ababsa et al., 2013)

Jordan is the second most water-stressed country in the world (UNICEF, 2021). Jordan's annual renewable water resources at(100m3/person) are well below the threshold of 500m3/person defining severe water scarcity. In urban areas, water is usually available once a week, and less than once in two weeks in rural areas (UNICEF,

2021). In summer, the weekly frequency is lower, as well as the pumping pressure in pipelines is severed which makes it hard to reach top stories in residential buildings, especially in the urban setting, where inhabitants rely on water tanks installed on the roof of each building to cover the needs for the upcoming week/s.

The agricultural sector in Jordan depletes nearly half of the country's water supply consumption and only contributes four percent to the gross domestic product (GDP) of the once-agricultural country (USAID, 2021).

Settlement Patterns

Jordan has three distinct climate regions (Ministry of Environment, 2014) (USAID 2017):

- **Jordan valley**, a section of the great rift valley, with an elevation below sea level. It experiences warm winters and hot summers, and an average annual rainfall of 102-300 mm.
- The **Badia** (Arabic for desert) covers 85% of the country with an arid and semi-arid climate, with an average annual rainfall below 200 mm, which renders it an inhospitable habitat for humans.
- The **Highlands**, which span north to south of Jordan to the east of the Jordan valley. It experiences the highest average annual rainfall of 350-500 mm and hosts vast majority of Jordan's rural and urban settlements.

Because of the biophysical nature of Jordan, 90% of the population is in the northwest of the country, where the climate is temperate, and water is abundant which makes the population density of that part one of the highest in the world. Population growth is rapid in Jordan attributed to enormous waves of refugees mainly from Palestinian territories, Iraq, and Syria following political and societal upheavals in the region. Making Jordan one of the highest refugee host countries in the world (on a per capita basis) (UNHCR, 2017) (Government of the Netherlands, 2019).

Conflict-induced population growth, besides considerable rural-to-urban migration induced by systematic livelihood challenges at least partly stemming from water-energy scarcities and their implications on agricultural profitability/feasibility. Rapid population growth further strains the already contested resources, infrastructure, and social services. As one of the worlds' most water-stressed countries (UNICEF, 2021), water scarcity affects every aspect of the people of Jordan's lives and impedes economic growth and development (USAID, 2017).

2. Jordan Emission Profile

While water scarcity dominates Jordan's immediate challenges, its emission profile highlights its contribution—and vulnerability—to broader climate issues. The energy sector in Jordan at a staggering 72.9% of the total GHG emission of the country for the year 2006, the vast majority of which (99.8%) is carbon dioxide (Ministry of Environment, 2014), shows that the country has a higher energy intensity of GDP than most countries of the MENA region. Still, Jordan only contributes (0.06%-0.07%) (worldometers, 2021) (USAID, 2016) to global GHG emissions. According to the Third National Communication (TNC) (2014), Jordan is projected to be highly vulnerable to the risks of climate change, especially the increase in temperature, dry spells, and the decrease of precipitation (Ministry of Environment, 2014).

3. Jordan's Climate-Driven Risks Profile

Below is an overview of the projections related to Jordan, as in the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Fifth report and illustrated in the 2014 Jordan's third national communication to the UNFCCC.

Future Climate Projections

Jordan's projections of two Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change IPCC's *Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs)* namely RCP4.5 and RCP8.5, on the 1980-2100 period, show that by 2085 **mean temperature** is "extremely likely" to have a homogenous increase of temperature all over different geographical regions of the

country. Ranging between +3.1C° and +5.1C° for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 respectively (Ministry of Environment, 2014).

Also, by 2085, the **minimum temperature** is “extremely likely” to have an increase ranging between +1.7C° and +5.3C° for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 respectively (Ministry of Environment, 2014). The **maximum temperature** is “extremely likely” to have an increase ranging between +1.7C° and +5.5C° by 2085 for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 respectively (Ministry of Environment, 2014).

Forecasted **precipitation** using RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 shows that it is "likely" to have a trend of significant decrease in precipitation. Yet, soaked years may still be "likely possible" by the end of the century (Ministry of Environment, 2014).

The **Potential Evapotranspiration (PET)** will likely increase to 250 millimeters by the end of the 21st century. PET will increase in the country overall but with varying intensities, but the highest increment will be in the following regions: most intense in the country's eastern desert, followed by the coastal city of Aqaba and southern regions.

Under the same study (Ministry of Environment, 2014) for the same scenarios on the 1980-2100 period calculations of the **Standardized Precipitation indexes (SPI)**, which is a drought index sensitive to global warming (Vicente-Serrano, 2010), have shown that it "extremely likely" for Jordan to witness more droughts. Contrarily, it is also "likely" to above-average wet years to occur that may generate floods.

Four Climate Hazards

The projected changes in Jordan's climate variables (minimum, maximum, and median temperature, precipitation, PET, and SPI) exacerbate the following **four climate hazards**: decreased precipitation, increased temperature, evaporation, and ultimately drought. It's worth mentioning the repercussions of the hazards remain serious for both the median and the worst-case pathways, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 respectively. These climate hazards cascade into risks across vital sectors, further threatening Jordan's socio-economic stability

Sectoral Vulnerabilities

The previously discussed forecasted changes in climate variables, and the resulting climate hazards will directly amplify and generate risks in the vital sectors, as follows according to a 2017 USAID risk profiling of Jordan (Also based on the 2014 IPCC).

The **Agricultural** sector is already operating in a vulnerable state, as thoroughly mentioned in the introduction, stricken by water scarcity and high-water usage. Adding to that the nature of the urban sprawl on the expense on Jordan's most fertile lands and temperate climate regions since the establishment of Transjordan (al-Asad, 2004). Thus, agricultural activities are pushed into the eastern and southern fronts, which suffer soil degradation and more frequent drought risk. Furthermore, agriculture in such lands increasingly depends on irrigation. The ability to maintain such lands may be compromised under climate change scenarios, given the temperature rise and rainfall decrease.

The resulting risks (USAID, 2017):

- Crop loss and failures due to volatile and diminished rainfall.
- Increased demand for irrigation water due to higher evaporation and evapotranspiration, with decreased ability to meet such demand.
- Shortened and altered growing seasons.
- Desertification of already scarce arable land.
- Income loss, and inability to grow water-intensive export crops.
- Increased food imports.

The **Livestock** sector is already dwindling due to the decline in pastures, and failures in fodder crops such as barley.

The sectors' main stressors, as in agriculture, remain the rising temperature, decreased rainfall, and drought augmenting the following risks:

- Higher livestock morbidity, and mortality.
- Scarcity of livestock drinking water and pasturelands.
- Eventually, loss of income and trade deficit.

Human Health

Increased reliance on treated water carries the risks of crop contamination, waterborne pathogens and ultimately jeopardizing food security in a country that imports 80% of domestic food demands.

Water Availability

The water supply crisis in Jordan is worsened by two fundamental factors: (i) The country is a downstream country and depends on upstream nations Syria and Israel for its surface water supply where the headwaters for the transboundary Yarmouk and Jordan rivers are located. (ii) groundwater pumping intensification at approximately 200% of the sustainable capacity. Even the newly developed "Disi" aquifer, on which Amman partly relies, is a transboundary aquifer with Saudi Arabia (Rajsekhar et al., 2017).

Water sector risks, caused by rising temperatures and reduced rainfall, including but not limited to constrained economic growth; reduced recharge rate, groundwater, and surface water; reduced water quality, and regional geopolitical tension over water (USAID, 2017).

4. Tipping Point and Policy Recommendations

Jordan's resources issue, or food-water-energy trilemma, is multi-faceted in nature, spanning domestic scarcities, land-use changes in neighboring upstream nations, massive refugee influx, and climate change as a threat multiplier (Jordan Ministry of Water and Irrigation, 2016). Those elements comprise multiple interdependencies, conflicts, and trade-offs when tackling each in isolation. For instance, a displacement (or migration) wave, driven by decreased agricultural livelihood, into Jordan's fertile-urban north will further exacerbate arable land and water scarcities. Simultaneously, this climate change may drive land-use changes in the upstream nations and may intensify irrigation, which will imperil Jordan's water share, creating cascading impacts. While policies and international partnerships offer hope, their implementation must align with holistic and adaptive strategies. By prioritizing resource optimization, sustainable development, and community resilience, Jordan can mitigate these challenges and set a regional example for climate adaptation.

References

- Britannica. (2021, 08 20). *Settlement patterns*. Retrieved from Britannica: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Jordan/Settlement-patterns>
- D Rajsekhar, S. G. (2017). Increasing drought in Jordan: Climate change and cascading Syrian land-use impacts on reducing. *SCIENCE ADVANCES*.
- UNDP. (2021, 06 17). *World Day to Combat Desertification and Drought*. Retrieved from www.jo.undp.org: <https://www.jo.undp.org/content/jordan/en/home/presscenter/articles/2021/world-day-to-combat-desertification-and-drought.html>
- The World Bank. (2021, 08 20). World Bank Country and Lending Groups Retrieved from datahelpdesk.worldbank.org: <https://datahelpdesk.worldbank.org/knowledgebase/articles/906519-world-bank-country-and-lending-groups>
- WTO Committee on Agriculture (2017). WTO LIST OF NET FOOD-IMPORTING DEVELOPING COUNTRIES FOR THE PURPOSES OF THE MARRAKESH MINISTERIAL DECISION ON MEASURES CONCERNING THE

POSSIBLE NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF THE REFORM PROGRAMME ON LEAST-DEVELOPED AND NET FOOD-IMPORTING DEVELOPING COUNTRIES ("THE DECISION"). G/AG/5/Rev.11.

Government of the Netherlands (2019). Climate Change Profile. Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

USAID (2017). CLIMATE CHANGE RISK PROFILE JORDAN. Retrieved from www.climatelinks.org/sites/default/files/asset/document/2017_USAID_Climate%20Change%20Risk%20Profile_Jordan.pdf

MOENV, U. (2014). Jordan's third national communication on climate change. Ministry of Environment (MOENV) and United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Amman, Jordan. Retrieved from <https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/migration/arabstates/climate-change-from-batir-smaller-version.pdf>

UNHCR (June 2017) Jordan Factsheet: <https://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/Jordan%20Fact%20Sheet%20June%202017-%20FINAL.pdf>

UNICEF. (2021, 18 08). *Jordan; Water, sanitation and hygiene Access to safe water and sanitation for every child*. Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/>: <https://www.unicef.org/jordan/water-sanitation-and-hygiene>

Olivier, J. G. J., et al. "Emission database for global atmospheric research (EDGAR)." *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 31.1 (1994): 93-106.

USAID (2016). Greenhouse Gas Emissions in Jordan.

Vicente-Serrano, S. M., Beguería, S., & López-Moreno, J. I. (2010). A multiscalar drought index sensitive to global warming: the standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index. *Journal of climate*, 23(7), 1696-1718.

USAID. (2021, August 30). *WATER RESOURCES & ENVIRONMENT*. Retrieved from <https://www.usaid.gov/>: <https://www.usaid.gov/jordan/water-and-wastewater-infrastructure>

worldometers. (2021, 08 09). *Jordan CO2 Emissions*. Retrieved from worldometers: <https://www.worldometers.info/co2-emissions/jordan-co2-emissions/>

Ababsa, M. (Ed.) p. 257-267. (2013). *Atlas of Jordan: history, territories and society* (Vol. 32). Presses de l'Ifpo.

al-Asad, M. (2004, April 29). *Urban Sprawl Urban Crossroads#3*. Retrieved from CSBE: <https://www.csbe.org/urban-sprawl>

Ministry of Water and Irrigation (2016) *Climate Change Policy for a Resilient Water Sector* available at <https://www.greengrowthknowledge.org/national-documents/jordan-climate-change-policy-resilient-water-sector>